

EnergyGuard Data Lake Architecture: From Heterogeneous Ingestion to Federated Data Sharing

José L. Hernández¹^e and Gabriele Balzano⁴

¹Energy department, CARTIF technology centre, Parque tecnológico Boecillo, Boecillo, Spain

²Institute of Communication and Computer Systems, National Technical University of Athens, Athens, Greece

³Metasymbiose, 4 Rue des Frères Lumière, 78370 Plaisir, France

⁴Hal Service S.R.L., Regione Torame, 16, 13011 Borgosesia VC, Italy

josher@cartif.es, {vkarakolis, tpountridis, smouzakitis}@epu.ntua.gr, hnn.metasymbiose@sfr.fr, gabriele.balzano@halservice.it

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Abstract: The increasing deployment of artificial intelligence, digital twins and advanced sensing technologies in the energy sector requires data infrastructures capable of managing heterogeneous sources, large-scale time series and strict security, privacy and governance requirements. This paper presents a modular Data Lake architecture designed to support trustworthy AI development, testing and validation in energy-related scenarios. The proposed solution provides a scalable pipeline for data ingestion, harmonisation and storage, while promoting interoperability through semantic modelling, metadata management and standardised interfaces. A layered architecture enables integration with external services and federated data sharing, ensuring controlled access, traceability and accountability across the data lifecycle. The resulting design provides a practical blueprint for secure and interoperable Data Lake platforms supporting AI-enabled energy systems experimentation.

1 INTRODUCTION

The rapid digitalisation of the energy sector is increasing the volume, velocity and diversity of data from smart meters, distributed energy resources, building management systems and IoT devices. At the same time, advanced analytics, artificial intelligence (AI) and digital twins rely on these data streams for optimisation and decision-making in decentralised energy infrastructures. These datasets remain fragmented across organisations and technological silos, stored in heterogeneous formats and subject to strict privacy and regulatory constraints (Wehrmeister, 2025), complicating the development of scalable data management solutions that ensure reliable experimentation (Zhang, 2025).

Data lake architectures arise as a promising solution due to their flexibility in storing raw and semi-structured data at scale (GAIA-X, 2026). Nevertheless, without well-defined mechanisms for data ingestion, metadata management governance and access control, data lakes may rapidly deteriorate into poorly curated repositories. This risk is especially significant in energy-related applications, where reliable data sharing and interoperability are essential to enable cross-domain analysis. In response, federated data infrastructures and data space initiatives (e.g., GAIA-X and the International Data Spaces reference architecture) (Otto, 2021) emphasise the need for enforceable governance policies, secure and auditable exchange mechanisms.

^a <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7621-2937>

^b <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2833-3088>

^c <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9769-7665>

^d <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9616-447X>

^e <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7976-6926>

In recent years, testing and experimentation Facilities (TEFs) have emerged as a key European instrument to accelerate the development, validation and market uptake of trustworthy AI solutions in the energy and building sector. By providing large-scale environments where innovations can be tested under realistic operational conditions, TEFs enable facility managers, network operators and other stakeholders to evaluate multiple scenarios without affecting real infrastructures (European Commission, 2023). Beyond conventional laboratory validation, they combine physical infrastructures, digital platforms and domain expertise to support end-to-end experimentation, including integration, performance evaluation and compliance assessment in complex cyber-physical energy systems.

Within this context, EnergyGuard (European Commission, 2025) is a Horizon Europe initiative establishing a pan-European TEF network for AI in the energy domain. The project integrates five facilities across Europe, including transmission networks, microgrids, distributed energy resources, hydrogen platforms, building digital twins and renewable energy communities. This diversity enables experimentation across the energy value chain and supports validation workflows combining real infrastructures and digital twins.

The role of a TEF-oriented data lake extends beyond traditional scalable storage. It must support the full data lifecycle (Hernández, 2023a) required for rigorous experimentation. This includes not only continuous ingestion from heterogeneous sources, but also mechanisms for cleaning, harmonisation and enrichment (Hernández, 2024a). A major challenge in this context lies in guaranteeing interoperability across facilities, technologies and stakeholders. TEFs also require robust governance mechanisms to enable data sharing without compromising confidentiality, security or compliance.

This paper faces the previous challenges by the design of a data lake architecture as a reference solution for TEF-oriented experimentation in the energy and building domains. This work proposes a modular, layered framework for end-to-end data lifecycle management, including heterogeneous data ingestion, harmonisation, semantic enrichment and controlled access for secure sharing. The architecture integrates governance and interoperability principles aligned with federated data ecosystems, enabling traceable and reusable datasets for AI validation and digital twin experimentation across distributed energy infrastructures.

2 CURRENT PRACTICES

Data lakes have become a widely adopted paradigm for managing large-scale and heterogeneous datasets, particularly where traditional data warehouses struggle with the volume, variety and velocity of modern data sources (Sawadogo, 2020). Unlike schema-on-write approaches, data lakes follow a schema-on-read principle (Hai, 2021), allowing raw data to be ingested and structured later according to analytical needs. This flexibility supports diverse analytical workloads, from exploratory analysis to machine learning, and has led to layered architectures separating ingestion, storage, processing and access.

Current practices recognise that data lakes must incorporate systematic metadata management, curation processes and governance mechanisms (Sawadogo, 2019). Modern implementations integrate metadata catalogues, lineage tracking and data quality management to enable dataset discovery, interpretability and reuse (Chen, 2022; Sawadogo, 2020). As a result, metadata modelling has become a central research challenge, since data usability in data lakes depends on semantic descriptions, dataset relationships and operational traceability (Sawadogo, 2019; Sawadogo, 2020; Chen, 2022).

In the building and energy sectors, data lakes are increasingly used to integrate heterogeneous datasets such as smart meter readings, building management signals, weather data and maintenance logs (Al Dakheel, 2020). This integration enables advanced analytics for forecasting, fault detection and energy optimisation (Mocanu, 2016), particularly when combining high-frequency timeseries data with contextual information distributed across different systems and stakeholders.

Semantic building data platforms have been proposed to improve interoperability and discovery, enabling analytics applications to interact with harmonised datasets through higher-level query mechanisms (Hugo et al., 2023). Recent systematic reviews highlight the growing adoption of data-driven approaches in smart buildings, while stressing the persistent challenges of data heterogeneity, quality, and contextual enrichment needed for robust energy management solutions (Hernández, 2024c).

Recent work in smart buildings suggests that data lakes should evolve from passive repositories into open and federated data ecosystems capable of supporting cross-domain energy services (Hernández, 2023a). However, the current landscape remains dominated by data silos, where heterogeneous datasets, such as energy systems, comfort monitoring, BIM (Building Information

Modelling), EPCs (Energy Performance Contracts), are fragmented, limiting interoperability and the deployment of reliable analytics and decision-support tools (Hernández, 2024c). Data lake architectures increasingly support the full data lifecycle, including ingestion, integration, transformation and exploitation layers, while embedding data quality mechanisms as core architectural requirements (Hernández, 2023b). This approach ensures curated, traceable and standardised datasets for reliable energy-related services across building domains.

A key trend in this literature is the integration of dynamic timeseries data from sensors and meters with static contextual data such as BIM or CityGML assets through semantic linking mechanisms, enabling richer representations of building operation and infrastructure context (Hernández, 2024b). By combining timeseries databases, object storage, graph databases and data marts, data lakes can support domain-specific pre-analytics, scalable querying and downstream AI services (Hernández, 2024c). This approach often relies on knowledge graphs based on RDF and ontologies to link real-world assets with data streams, improving discoverability, reuse and interoperability. Such architectures also depend on robust ETL pipelines adapted to heterogeneous protocols (e.g., MQTT, API, FTP, SQL) and data formats (CSV, JSON, text), enabling data ingestion, harmonisation, metadata extraction and synchronisation between dynamic and static repositories (Hernández, 2024a).

Despite the growing adoption of data lakes in the building and energy sectors, challenges remain regarding semantic interoperability, data quality and privacy-preserving management. Energy consumption and occupancy data may reveal sensitive behavioural patterns, while AI-driven decision support requires reliable and traceable datasets. In multi-stakeholder environments, heterogeneous governance policies further hinder cross-domain reuse without mechanisms for harmonisation, provenance and access control. Therefore, scalable storage must be complemented with metadata-driven governance, reproducible workflows and interoperability frameworks to enable trustworthy analytics (Alreshidi et al., 2024).

2.1 Contributions beyond the current practices

The data lake architecture presented in this analysis, developed within the EU EnergyGuard project (European Commission, 2025), introduces an advanced data lake architecture that incorporates a

semantic layer to align heterogeneous measurements, entities and operational concepts under a shared representation. By coupling ontology-based modelling with the data ingestion and validation processes, the proposed solution enables machine-actionable metadata, reducing ambiguity in the interpretation of variables, assets and system states. This semantic foundation is essential to ensure that datasets originating from different TEFs can be systematically compared, combined and reused across experimentation campaigns, supporting consistent AI training, validation and benchmarking.

In addition, it addresses the growing need for trusted and controlled data sharing through an access-controlled approach in which datasets can be exposed via standardised interfaces and intelligent querying services. As the same time, it preserves traceability, provenance and the authority of data providers over usage conditions. Such capabilities are particularly critical in federated experimentation settings, where multiple stakeholders must collaborate across organisational boundaries and where the accountability of AI-driven decisions depends directly on the integrity, reliability and provenance of the underlying data assets.

Finally, the proposed architecture supports the full data lifecycle through a modular and layered framework integrating multiple storage backends and specialised services. This enables the combined management of structured, semi-structured and unstructured datasets, while accommodating both real-time ingestion and historical data exploitation. As a result, the EnergyGuard data lake provides a scalable and interoperable foundation for TEF-oriented experimentation, enabling reproducible and trustworthy AI evaluation across distributed energy and building infrastructures.

3 DATA LAKE APPROACH

The data lake is conceived as the core data backbone enabling secure and trustworthy experimentation. The data management architecture is designed as a modular framework covering the complete data lifecycle, from raw data ingestion to high-level interoperable data sharing. It explicitly follows the principles of interoperability, semantics, privacy and governance by design.

Figure 1 depicts the data lake approach, which connects data originating from TEF repositories through tailored ETL pipelines. These harmonised datasets are saved into two complementary storage domains: a Data Warehouse (DWH) for timeseries

and dynamic information (Hernández, 2023b), and a repository for static or contextual datasets. Therefore, a synchronisation mechanism is required to ensure consistency between these two domains, enabling coherent access and combined exploitation in downstream services. Intelligent querying provides enriched and harmonised data views to share data. By combining data from timeseries and static repositories, data marts are created and exposed through a dedicated API to facilitate integration with digital twins. Throughout this process, a transversal security and privacy layer ensures that data are handled under authorisation and anonymisation mechanisms, supporting data compliance.

Figure 1: EnergyGuard data lake conceptual approach

The data lake is deployed on High-Performance Computing (HPC) infrastructure to handle the computational and storage demands of TEF-scale experimentation. This enables scalable ETL execution and efficient processing of high-frequency monitoring data for AI training, digital twin simulations and benchmarking workflows while ensuring controlled access and governance.

3.1 Synchronisation mechanisms

To ensure semantic consistency between operational data storage and the knowledge representation layer, the data lake implements a bidirectional synchronisation workflow between the DWH and the static repository. As illustrated in Figure 2 (Hernández, 2024b), first stage is the population of the semantic repository (Ontology & semantics) in form of knowledge graph. Datasets coming from BIM, plans, Excel sheets, among others, are used to provide an initial input where the topology of the building or energy system can be mapped into such a knowledge graph. This represents the unique and trustworthy repository of information.

The customised ETLs (Hernández, 2024a), obtaining heterogeneous data streams are synced with the knowledge graph information. As represented in Figure 2, DWH initially gets the IDs for the sensors, smart meters or other assets / elements. The result of this query allows the population of the contextual

information of the DWH prior the ingestion of data. Once the ETL process has persisted new records, the DWH is aligned with ontology layer through the corresponding unique identifiers (get IDs). This method ensures that each element can be referenced consistently across both layers.

Figure 2: Semantically-driven approach for synchronising data samples

The workflow relies on a synchronisation mechanism that maintains coherence between the relational timeseries storage and the semantic knowledge graph. Changes in one layer, such as new measurements in the DWH or ontology updates, are reflected in the other through identifier-based linking and coordinated ETL processes, preventing semantic drift and ensuring harmonised and traceable data for querying and analytics. Although this approach introduces additional architectural complexity, the trade-off is justified in the TEF context, where semantic interoperability, traceability and reproducible experimentation across multiple facilities are essential.

4 DATA LAKE ARCHITECTURE

The proposed data management architecture, as a modular framework, is drawn in Figure 3. It supports the end-to-end data lifecycle, from raw data ingestion to high-level interoperable data sharing. It is conceived to operate in heterogeneous and distributed environments, enabling collection, harmonisation, storage and exploitation of data across the TEFs. The architecture embraces interoperability, semantics, privacy and governance by design, where each architectural layer fulfils a set of responsibilities:

- **Data Ingestion and Harmonisation** for the integration of structured and unstructured data from multiple heterogeneous sources. ETL-driven processing allow incoming datasets to be transformed into a common data model.
- The **Secure Data Lake** stores and manages both timeseries and contextual information, while enforcing data quality mechanisms.

Figure 3: Data lake modular architecture for the management of TEFs data samples

- The **Intelligent Querying** layer provides semantically enriched data access, enabling end-users and downstream services to retrieve harmonised information through SQL (Structured Query Language)-based queries.
- The **Interoperable Data Sharing** layer ensures that curated datasets can be securely exchanged through standardised APIs (Application Programming Interface), linked-data mechanisms, or federated data.
- **Security and Privacy** services provide cross-cutting mechanisms, ensuring that data remain protected throughout the entire lifecycle.
- Finally, the **Ontology and Semantics** layer provides a shared machine-interpretable representation of entities and measurements, supporting alignment across heterogeneous sources and improving interoperability during data integration and exploitation.

At the base of the architecture, the data sources layer represents the raw data level. Each TEF exposes data via different protocols, sampling frequencies and access mechanisms, increasing the complexity and heterogeneity of the data collection process.

4.1 Data Ingestion and Harmonisation layer

The Data Ingestion and Harmonisation layer acts as the gateway between TEF raw data sources and the data lake, acquiring heterogeneous datasets and converting them into a consistent representation before storage. This involves data collection, integration and transformation processes to ensure harmonised datasets.

The ingestion pipeline is implemented through dedicated ETL modules (ETL1...ETLn), each adapted to specific data providers and executed

periodically by a Scheduler. These ETLs are developed using Pentaho Data Integration (PDI) (Pentaho, 2026), where Transformations define processing logic and Jobs manage execution and scheduling. Raw data are ingested, filtered, transformed (e.g., type mapping, unit conversion, aggregation) and stored in the Data Lake for downstream services such as digital twins and AI experimentation.

To consolidate outputs from multiple ETLs, the architecture incorporates a Data Bus that integrates and formats data before storage. It includes a Data Integrator for merging outputs, a Data Model Formatter for mapping data to the common model, and a JDBC-based component for standardised interaction with target databases.

4.2 Secure Data Lake layer

The Secure Data Lake layer provides core services for protected storage, data curation and metadata management. It stores both temporal and contextual datasets while ensuring consistency and traceability across the data lifecycle. A key design choice is the separation between dynamic timeseries data and static contextual information, maintained through the synchronisation mechanism.

- Timeseries database: stores dynamic datasets such as sensor and meter measurements, implemented using PostgreSQL with TimescaleDB and PostGIS extensions.
- Static data database: stores contextual and descriptive information using graph technologies (e.g., GraphDB).

Beyond storage, the layer includes data curation mechanisms to prepare datasets for digital twins and AI experimentation. A Data Quality service performs validation and correction through a Checker (completeness and consistency assessment) and a Corrector, which applies predefined rules to repair data (Hernández, 2024d; Hernández, 2025).

The layer also includes a data catalogue for metadata management, enabling dataset indexing, discovery and semantic exploration. It comprises a catalogue database for metadata storage and a search engine supporting attribute-based queries.

4.3 Intelligent Querying layer

The Intelligent Querying layer serves as the main access point for retrieving harmonised datasets from the EnergyGuard data lake. Its objective is to simplify data consumption by providing intuitive and

semantically enriched access, reducing the complexity of sharing and exploiting heterogeneous information. By integrating business intelligence capabilities, this layer supports the generation of pre-analytics and pre-processed views, enabling users and services to access curated and structured data.

This layer is composed of: (i) an SQL query engine that executes standard queries across both dynamic and static repositories while abstracting underlying database complexity; (ii) Business Intelligence tools that combine, aggregate and queried data to produce domain-specific insights and data marts; (iii) a Data Enricher that adds contextual and semantic information to time-series values; and (iv) data marts, which store optimised, topic-oriented subsets of curated data to improve performance and usability for specific applications (e.g., energy demand forecasting or fault detection).

4.4 Interoperable Data Sharing layer

The Interoperable Data Sharing layer enables secure, standardised and semantically interoperable data exchange across different entities and stakeholders. It builds on the curated outputs provided by the data marts, where datasets are prepared for external consumption and collaboration. To ensure that shared information remains both machine-readable and unambiguous, data are formatted into a common representation such as JSON-LD (JavaScript Object Notation for Linked Data) and are exposed through standard APIs. This approach supports consistent interpretation and facilitates integration with data consumers. The components are:

- Federated data services, enabling decentralised access and querying without requiring all datasets to be stored in a central repository.
- JSON-LD, used as a linked-data format to support semantic interoperability and preserve contextual meaning during exchange.
- APIs, providing programmatic access to shared datasets and supporting integration with external tools and services.

Also, within this layer, connection with data spaces is provided in order to represent collaborative environments where stakeholders can publish and access shared data under common standards, governance policies and usage rules.

4.5 Security and Privacy

The Privacy and Security layer provides transversal protection mechanisms across the full data lifecycle, ensuring compliance with data protection regulations

and the application of cybersecurity best practices. Its purpose is to guarantee that data are processed, stored and shared under controlled and auditable conditions, preventing unauthorised access and mitigating privacy risks. Key functions of this layer include auditing, access control, encryption, authorisation and anonymisation.

4.6 Ontology and Semantics

Semantic consistency across distributed facilities is ensured through the Ontology and Semantics layer, which provides a shared, machine-interpretable representation of entities, measurements and their relationships. Synchronised with the data lake, this layer enables continuous validation of datasets against semantic schemas while supporting the evolution of new assets and variables, enabling interoperable and reproducible AI validation workflows across federated energy infrastructures.

The layer formalises the data model using standardised entities and relationships, enabling semantic search, consistent interpretation and cross-domain reuse of datasets. The common data model builds on widely used ontologies and standards to ensure semantic interoperability and consistent measurement semantics. Table 1 summarises the core ontologies applied across TEFs. Rather than merging all ontologies into a single unified schema, the architecture adopts a modular alignment strategy in which each ontology covers a specific semantic domain (e.g., sensors, devices, building topology or datasets).

Table 1: Primary Semantic Standards and Vocabularies for EnergyGuard data lake models

Standard / Vocabulary	Purpose	Usage value
Semantic Sensor Network Ontology (SOSA)	Domain-independent model to describe sensors, observations, acquisition processes, sampling frequencies...	Measurement timeseries. Attach sensors, features of interest, and deployment metadata.
Smart Application REference (SAREF)	Representation of devices, their functions, services, and energy-related capabilities.	Device classification, functional capabilities, and service roles.
SAREF4ENER (Energy Extension of SAREF)	SAREF extension, including energy flows / profiles, storage, power generation, and demand response.	PV systems, batteries, consumption/production flows, flexibility behaviour.

DCAT (Data Catalog Vocabulary)	Standard for describing datasets, distributions, publishers, formats, provenance, and metadata.	Cataloguing pilot datasets and describing ETL outputs.
Brick Schema	Comprehensive building/system topology covering HVAC, zones, equipment...	Sensor placement, HVAC equipment, meters...
BOT (Building Topology Ontology)	Canonical representation of building structure, spaces, zones, and building elements.	Spatial hierarchy, geometry of buildings, floors, spaces...
REC (Real Estate Core)	Real estate assets, buildings, units, spaces...	Energy audits, renovations, EPCs.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented the EnergyGuard data lake architecture as a modular and governance-ready framework for data management in Testing and Experimentation Facilities (TEFs) in the energy and building domains. The architecture supports the full data lifecycle, including heterogeneous ingestion, harmonisation, secure storage, semantically enriched querying and interoperable data sharing, enabling scalable management of real-time and historical datasets across distributed infrastructures.

A key contribution is the integration of an Ontology and Semantics layer that provides a shared, machine-interpretable representation of entities, measurements and relationships across pilots. This semantic foundation improves data interpretation, reuse and replicability across heterogeneous environments while supporting reproducible AI experimentation and cross-domain analytics. Data quality services further enhance dataset discoverability, traceability and reliability.

Although the architecture has been designed and deployed within the EnergyGuard TEF infrastructure, this work focuses primarily on architectural design rather than full quantitative evaluation. Future work will validate the architecture through experimentation campaigns across the EnergyGuard TEFs, reporting indicators such as integrated data sources, connected assets, ingestion frequency, data volumes, ETL execution times and representative query scenarios to benchmark scalability, interoperability and governance under realistic conditions.

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